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Impact of anteroposterior pelvic diameter on ^{99m}Tc -mercaptoacetyltriglycine diuretic renography

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Introduction: Antenatal hydronephrosis is the most commonly detected abnormality during fetal development. The aim of the study was to evaluate whether the size of the prenatal and postnatal renal pelvic anteroposterior diameter (APD) has prediction of obstruction drainage finding on diuretic renography and impaired renal function.

Methods: We prospectively studied 32 renal units with prenataly diagnosed hydronephrosis, that was confirmed on postnatal ultrasonography. The renal pelvic APD was measured in pregnancy between 17th and 35th week of gestation, and between 1st and 4th week after birth to confirm hydronephrosis. The initial ^{99m}Tc -MAG3 was performed in all patients between 4th and 8th week after birth. All patients were divided into two groups: the first group included patients with obstructive diuretic renography finding and the second one included patients with non-obstructive finding.

Results: Out of 32 renal units with hydronephrosis, 14 had obstructive pattern on diuretic renography, and 18 had non-obstructive hydronephrosis. The average of prenatal renal pelvic APD in the first group was statistically higher than in the second one ($p=0.009$). The average of postnatal renal pelvic APD in the obstructive group was also statistically higher than in the non-obstructive group ($p=0.0006$). The presence of impaired renal function (less than 40%) was significantly more frequent in the obstructive group.

Conclusion: Our study showed that the grade of both renal pelvic diameter, more prominent postnatal, have a significant impact on scintigraphy finding.

Key words: Hydronephrosis; Kidney Pelvis; Ultrasonography; Prenatal Diagnosis; Radioisotope Renography; Infant, Newborn; Technetium Tc 99m Mertiotide

UDC: 616.65-006:616.71:616-072

Correlation between Gleason score level, prostate specific antigen levels and bone scintigraphy in newly diagnosed prostatic cancer patients

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Introduction: The aim of this study was to identify correlation between Gleason score (GS), and prostate specific antigen levels (PSA), with bone metastasis in newly diagnosed prostate cancer patients.

Methods: This retrospective study included 298 patients with prostatic cancer in region of Vojvodina from 2012 to 2014., who had PSA, histological confirmation of prostatic cancer (GS) and bone scan. PSA was measured using hemiluminescent method, on Architect i2000SR automatic system, and histological examination was graded according to Gleason's grading system as: well differentiated ($GS \leq 6$), moderately differentiated ($GS = 7$), and poorly differentiated ($GS \geq 8$). Bone scintigraphy was performed 2 to 4 hours after i.v application of radiotracer agent ^{99m}Tc - diphosphonate (DPD) in dose of 555 MBq. The patients were divided into 2 groups based on bone scintigraphy findings.

Results: The patients with negative bone scan (129/298) had the average level of PSA 14 ng/ml, the mean age was 69.8 $\pm$ 6.4 years and GS was 6.5 $\pm$ 1.24. The patients with positive bone scan (169/298) finding had the average PSA level 50 ng/ml, mean age was 70 $\pm$ 7 years and GS was 7.4 $\pm$ 1.3. The patients with normal scintigraphic finding had statistically significant lower values of serum PSA ($p < 0.0001$) and Gleason score ($p < 0.0001$), comparing to patients with positive bone scan. The correlation between those parameters was better in group of patients with positive bone scan (Spearman correlation $r=0.4$).

Conclusion: The baseline level of PSA more than 50 ng/ml and Gleason score higher than 7 are excellent predictors of positive bone scan in patients with newly diagnosed prostatic cancer.

Key words: Prostatic Neoplasms; Radionuclide Imaging; Neoplasm Grading; Prostate-Specific Antigen; Neoplasm Metastasis; Bone Neoplasms

UDC: 616-006:616.071:616.71

Is Technetium-99- 2-methoxyisobutylisnitrile uptake in newly diagnosed multiple myeloma correlated with extense of disease activity?

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Technetium-99m 2-methoxyisobutylisnitrile (Tc-99m-MIBI) has been proposed as a useful tracer for the detection of disease sites in patients with multiple myeloma (MM).

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the role of the Tc-99m-MIBI uptake in disease detection and to assess the correlation between the uptake of this scintigraphy agent and prognostic factors in newly diagnosed MM patients.

Thirty-two untreated patients with multiple myeloma were studied using Tc-99m-MIBI. Anterior and posterior whole-body imaging were obtained 10 min after I.V. injection of 370 MBq Tc-99m-MIBI and scored according to intensity (I) and extent (E) of the radiotracer uptake. A summed score (SS) for the Tc-99m MIBI scan was calculated for each patient. The correlation between known prognostic factors of MM and a SS of Tc-99m-MIBI uptake was assessed.

There was a positive correlation between a SS of Tc-99m-MIBI uptake and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR; $r=0.553$, $P = 0.001$), C-reactive protein (CRP; $r=0.434$, $P = 0.01$), β_2 -microglobulin (β_2M ; $r=0.358$, $P = 0.04$), fibrinogen ($r=0.463$, $P = 0.008$) and bone marrow plasma cell infiltration ($r=0.613$, $P = 0.0001$). An inverse correlation was found between a SS of Tc-99m-MIBI uptake and hemoglobin ($r=0.442$, $P = 0.012$) and serum albumin ($r=0.603$, $P = 0.0003$).

In conclusion, the results of this study suggest that a higher uptake of the radiotracer correlated with more extensive disease activity, as determined by high levels of CRP, β_2M , fibrinogen and bone marrow plasma cell infiltration.

Key words: Multiple Myeloma; Diagnostic Imaging; Technetium Tc 99m Sestamibi; Prognosis

UDC: 616.12-073.7:616.071

Comparison of left ventricular functional parameters evaluated by quantitative ECG-gated SPECT and echocardiography

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Introduction: Prognosis and therapeutic decisions are often based on functional parameters of left ventricle (LV) such as: end-diastolic volume (EDV), end-systolic volume (ESV) and LV ejection fraction (LVEF), which means that these parameters need to be accurately measured. This can be done by many imaging modalities. Each of these modalities is subject to measurement errors that can lead to the inaccurate calculation of these parameters. The aim of this study was to compare the LV functional parameters calculated using quantitative electrocardiography (ECG)-gated myocardial perfusion single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) with those measured by ultrasound echocardiography (UCG).

Methods: We examined 40 patients (20 men and 20 women). In both groups we had the same number of patients with and without the presence of prior myocardial infarction. By the gated SPECT using technetium (Tc)-99m methoxyisobutylisnitrile (MIBI) perfusion and 4DM software, we calculated the following parameters: LV end-diastolic volume (EDV), end-systolic volume (ESV), ejection fraction (EF). The same parameters were measured by UCG. The measurements were performed within 6 month of each other. No new cardiac events were registered and no interventions were performed between measuring. The correlations between the cardiac parameters by UCG and those by SPECT/4DM were examined by linear regression analysis. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results: There was a significant correlation between EDV, ESV and EF measured by SPECT/MIBI and UCG (EDV, $r = 0.71$, $p < 0.001$; ESV, $r = 0.82$, $p < 0.001$; EF, $r = 0.75$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The LV systolic and diastolic parameters evaluated by SPECT/4DM correlated with those by UCG. The SPECT/4DM offers useful information regarding functional parameters of left ventricle in both men and women. Although the correlation between values obtained with gated-SPECT and blood pool ventriculography was acceptable, the differences show that the two techniques cannot be considered equivalent.

Key words: Cardiac-Gated Single-Photon Emission Computed-Assisted Tomography; Echocardiography; Myocardial Perfusion Imaging; Gated Blood-Pool Imaging; Ventricular Function, Left

UDC: 616.447:616.441:616-008.6

Uncommon primary presentation of multiple endocrine neoplasia – case report

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Introduction: Multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1 (MEN 1) is a syndrome characterized by neoplasia involving the parathyroid glands, enteropancreatic tumors, anterior pituitary adenoma and other neuro-endocrine tumors with variable penetrance. MEN 1 has estimated prevalence of 2 – 20 per 100 000 in the general population. Although the most commonly involved gland is the parathyroid gland, the variable penetrance of several neoplastic components can make the differential diagnosis and treatment challenging. We report herein the case of MEN 1 based on clinical, biochemical and pathological studies.

Case: The patient was a 49-year-old woman, who presented with acromegaly caused by pituitary adenoma. She underwent transsphenoidal resection of adenoma and was on bromokriptin therapy. After six years she was admitted to hospital because of reevaluation of active acromegaly. In further diagnostics there were found elevated PTH level (125.8 pg/ml) with normal ionized calcium levels and slightly elevated bone turnover markers and euthyroid nodular goiter. Dual phase parathyroid scintigraphy with ^{99m}Tc-MIBI showed adenoma of right superior parathyroid gland and hot nodule in left lobe of thyroid gland. She underwent parathyroidectomy due to enlarged right superior parathyroid gland that was shown histologically to be a parathyroid adenoma.

Conclusion: Although MEN 1 syndrome is most commonly primarily presented as hyperparathyroidism, patients with pituitary adenoma as potential presentations of MEN 1, should be monitored to prevent complications of developed syndrome.

Key words: Multiple Endocrine Neoplasia Type 1

UDC: 616-006:616-052:2-468.6

Separation of strontium and yttrium by supported liquid membrane extraction

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Introduction: Radionuclide ⁹⁰Y is one of the most suitable radionuclide for the radiotherapy of solid and non-operable malignant tumors. ⁹⁰Sr is an ideal source for obtaining carrier-free ⁹⁰Y. The aim of the present study was to investigate the separation of Y(III) from Sr(II) by supported liquid membrane extraction (SLME) in a hollow-fibre contactor under continuous mode of operation and using di(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid (DEHPA) as a carrier in the organic phase.

Methods: The SLME was performed in hollow fiber contactor containing polypropylene hollow fibers. The donor solution (25 mL of 500 ppm Sr(II) and 20 ppm Y(III) in 0.1 M HCl) was fed along the shell side of contactor in a recirculated mode of operation by a peristaltic pump (4.5 ml/min). The acceptor solution (4 mL of 3 M HCl) was fed along the lumen of the hollow fiber in a recirculated mode of operation by a peristaltic pump (0.8 ml/min). The concentrations of both metal ions were determined in donor and acceptor by Inductively Coupled Plasma - Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) solutions during the extraction which lasted 6 hrs.

Results: It was found that separation factor (α) depends on pH of aqueous solution, DEHPA concentration, and the organic solvent. The highest α (82900) was obtained from aqueous solution pH 1 (0.1 M HCl) and 15% DEHPA in n-dodecane.

The removal efficiency (R) of Y(III) increases during the SLME and reached the maximum of 85%. The extraction efficiency (E) of Y(III) also reised during the SLME, and after 6 hrs of extraction E is 60%. It means that 25% of extracted Y(III) was captured in the membrane. The changing of Sr(II) concentration in the donor solution was not observed. Also, Sr(II) was not detected in the acceptor phase.

Conclusion: The obtained results show that SLME is an effective method for separation Y(III) from Sr(II) and for obtaining carrier-free Y(III). The method described in this paper can be used for obtaining yttrium, suitable for therapeutic use in the treatment of non-operating tumors.

Key words: Pharmaceuticals Preparation; Radioisotopes; Strontium; Yttrium; Liquid-Liquid Extraction; Membranes, Artificial; Spectrophotometry, Atomic

UDC: 616.447:616-089.8:577.175.4

Diagnostic value of ^{99m}Tc -MIBI SPECT in preoperative localization for minimally invasive video assisted parathyroid surgery

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Introduction: Experienced surgeons can cure primary hyperparathyroidism with bilateral neck exploration in most patients (up to 95% of cases) without the aid of any preoperative imaging. Considering that a solitary parathyroid adenoma is the most frequent cause of primary hyperparathyroidism (in 80%–85%), bilateral neck exploration is considered overtreatment in most cases. Accurate preoperative localization is required to enable selective minimally invasive video assisted parathyroid surgery (MIVAP) and to reduce the operative failure rate.

Aim of the study: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the diagnostic value of early parathyroid SPECT as compared with planar imaging and color Doppler sonography (CDS) in patients undergoing MIVAP. A total of 15 consecutive patients with primary hyperparathyroidism underwent planar and SPECT parathyroid scintigraphy before MIVAP (dual-phase technique using ^{99m}Tc -methoxyisobutylisonitrile (^{99m}Tc -MIBI) and a double-tracer subtraction technique using a delayed ^{99m}Tc -pertechnetate scan).

Results: The average time for surgery was 35 min (range, 25–40 min). Serum calcium, phosphorus and parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels of patients before surgery was (Ca – 2.87 +/- 0.32 mmol/l, iCa – 1.4 +/- 0.2 mmol/l, P – 0.79 +/- 0.16, PTH – 185 pg/ml (Me)) and 24 h after surgery (Ca – 2.51 +/- 1.2 mmol/l, iCa – 1.1 +/- 1.2 mmol/l, P – 0.82 +/- 0.76, PTH – 100 pg/ml (Me)). All patients had histopathologic examination of the removed glands (single adenoma). SPECT was superior to planar imaging in 2 patients with multinodular goiters, compared with CDS in patients with goiters and ectopic adenoma. Planar parathyroid imaging (80%, 3 false negative findings) and CDS (74%, 4 false negative findings) are less sensitive compared with SPECT (93%, 1 false negative findings).

Conclusion: Preoperative scintigraphic imaging in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism is essential for accurate localization of parathyroid adenomas and for the selection of patients who are candidates for MIVAP.

Key words: Diagnostic Imaging; Preoperative Period; Technetium Tc 99m Sestamibi; Hyperparathyroidism, Primary; Video-Assisted Surgery; Tomography, Emission-Single-Photon; Ultrasonography, Doppler, Color

UDC: 616.447:616-091.8:615.07

Does BMI contribute negative scintigraphic findings in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism?

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Introduction: Localizing studies seem to be the key for determining the optimal surgical strategy in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism (PHPT). Understanding the factors that affect the accuracy of parathyroid localization test ^{99m}Tc -MIBI (MIBI) scanning will allow the surgeon to develop a successful surgical strategy in a given patient. **Aim:** The aim of this study was to identify factors that affect the success of localizing study in patients with PHPT.

Material and methods: The study group included 52 patients with PHPT who underwent MIBI scan and parathyroidectomy at Clinical centre of Vojvodina. The disease is in all cases verified pathohistologically. We analyze variables age, body mass index (BMI), ionizing calcium (Ca), phosphorus (P), serum PTH level, and gland volume (GV) versus the detection rate of individual abnormal glands on MIBI. Nonparametric tests for statistic significance and multiple regression analyses were used.

Results: Of the total of 56 abnormal glands analyzed, 92% involved single adenomas in PHPT and 8% double adenomas in PHPT. Scintigraphic sensitivity was 85%, 100 % specificity with 7 false negative findings. Patients with false negative findings were overweight, but not obese (BMI – 27 +/- 1.5 kg/m²) with lesser GV (median 12.5 cm³ oposite 27.3 cm³ in positive group), significantly lower ionised Ca and higher P. Serum PTH was not different between groups. In patients with negative scintigraphic findings we found negative significant correlation between BMI and GV (r -0.5).

Conclusion: Gland size is the strongest independent predictor of successful localization. Preoperatively, higher Ca levels, lower P in patients with lesser BMI are good indicators about the accuracy of localizing tests.

Key words: Hyperparathyroidism, Primary; Radionuclide Imaging; Technetium Tc 99m Sestamibi; Sensitivity and Specificity; Diagnostic Errors; Body Mass Index